

***Erotylidae* gen. nov. MS 5**
Cycad fungus beetle

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© Wild Cycad Conservation

Group: Insect

Size: 3.5 - 4.5 mm in length

Distribution:

Eastern Cape, near Kariega

Importance:

This cycad-associated beetle represents a previously unsequenced and undescribed lineage within the family *Erotylidae*. It forms part of the pollinator assemblage for endangered *Encephalartos* species. This genome and its sequencing will support the taxonomic description of this new genus and help clarify the evolutionary history of specialised insect-pollinator mutualisms in South Africa's threatened cycad flora.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 40.4 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 4.34 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.02 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.6% [Single: 96.3%, Duplicated: 2.3%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 4 516.77 kilobases

Contig number: 3 960

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Date Published: 2026-06-02

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20554694>

